

BASIC MOVEMENTS OF SPECIAL PHYSICAL TRAINING IN
TAEKWONDO

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Abstract: *This article presents the main movements of taekwondo. They introduce you to the taekwondo training of athletes and give you information about the exercises that athletes need.*

Keywords: *preparation process, taekwondo, basic exercises, strength training, skill development.*

The process of taekwondo training is a multifactorial system of using a variety of means, methods, organizational forms and material and technical conditions aimed at the development of an athlete in order to ensure his readiness for sporting achievements. The taekwondo training process includes training, training, competitions and out-of-competition factors that increase the effectiveness of training and competitions. The goal of training athletes is the maximum possible result in competitions. To achieve this goal, physical exercises are used as the main means of improving various physical qualities, abilities and other aspects of fitness, methods of training and training are determined, the intensity and intensity of physical exertion and the level of athletic training are planned. The main sections of taekwondo training are physical, technical, psychological, tactical and theoretical. The content of these sections of training depends on the contingent of students, their age, training experience, level of preparedness and the period of sports training. A taekwondo practitioner needs to be well physically prepared and have a high level of development of such physical qualities as speed, strength, flexibility and agility. In addition, it is necessary to have a high level of special endurance in order to be able to carry large training loads aimed at forming the correct technique of movements and successful performance in competitions. Physical training of a taekwondo practitioner is mainly aimed at educating his physical qualities that contribute to improving the technique of the movements performed. The need for separate physical training sessions is dictated by the specifics of taekwondo activities. The main training involves repeated execution of technical elements in order to improve the technique of strikes. During such training, the athlete mainly

uses his existing stock of physical qualities, and their increase in these conditions does not occur, because the efforts developed during the exercise, although very intense, are short-lived. Therefore, taekwondo practitioners conduct separate classes on general and special physical training, the volume of which sometimes reaches more than 50% of the total training time. General physical training (OFP) is aimed at the comprehensive physical development of all systems and body functions of athletes and is the basis for training special physical qualities and skills. The means of general physical training of taekwondists are: drill and general gymnastic exercises, mobile and sports games, walking, running, jumping, swimming, throwing, exercises with weights (weights, dumbbells, barbell) and other exercises aimed at developing strength, speed, flexibility and endurance. General physical training occupies an important place in the system of long-term training of taekwondists, being the basis of the motor activity of taekwondists. OFP is particularly important at the stage of initial training of young taekwondo athletes, when the foundations for long-term sports training are being laid. Special physical training is aimed at educating those physical qualities that ensure the successful development and performance of both simple and complex exercises at a high quality level. Special physical qualities for taekwondists are the strength and speed-strength qualities of the leg muscles, providing good jumping ability, the muscles of the trunk and arms, static and dynamic strength of the muscles of the arms and legs. Since athletes have to overcome mainly their own weight when performing jumps, then of all the indicators of strength for taekwondo athletes, the most important indicators are the absolute strength of the leg muscles and the relative strength of the muscles of the trunk and arms. The flexibility of a taekwondo practitioner is considered as the ability to perform punches and jumps with a large range of movements and is determined by the elasticity of muscles and ligaments. The most important thing is good mobility in the hip, ankle and shoulder joints, which contributes to the correct performance of technical actions. The endurance of a taekwondo practitioner is considered as the ability to perform complex coordination movements for a long time without reducing efficiency. The dexterity and coordination of a taekwondo practitioner have a pronounced specific character. It is known that the manifestation of dexterity, for example, in sports games does not guarantee success in gymnastics or taekwondo. For taekwondo practitioners, a specific manifestation of dexterity is the ability to maintain a stable balance, to subtly differentiate the spatial and temporal parameters of movements. The means of special physical training include physical exercises aimed at educating special physical qualities of a taekwondo practitioner.

When conducting strength training, it should be remembered that for taekwondo, its manifestation in combination with speed is most important and does not require an excessive increase in muscle mass, which can negatively affect the speed qualities of an athlete. Therefore, in the process of strength training, exercises aimed at developing the strength of muscle groups alternate with exercises aimed at educating speed, and the whole process is called speed-strength training. It is known that the manifestation of speed is limited by the appropriate coordination mechanisms, therefore, the methodology of speed education provides for performing exercises at extreme speeds that are co-ordinatively similar to competitive ones, while the exercises should be well mastered so that all attention when performing them is directed to speed. If the lack of strength does not make it possible to perform the movement at maximum speed, then it is necessary, by changing the position, to facilitate the execution of movements in this coordination, which will contribute to an increase in the speed capabilities of the athlete. When performing exercises that do not correspond to the athlete's strength capabilities, a "speed barrier" may arise for a while, which is very difficult to overcome. Therefore, in parallel with the education of speed, it is necessary to work on the development of the strength of this muscle group. To increase the strength of the muscles of the trunk, arms and legs, dynamic and static physical exercises are used without and with weights.

To develop strength, the following exercises are used: - with overcoming your own weight to failure; - static leg holds with short rest intervals. Carrying out strength exercises should alternate with performing stretching and speed exercises. The use of exercises performed with weights for small time periods contributes to the education of speed and strength qualities, after which exercises are performed without weights. This combination of exercises gives large increases in speed capabilities. A special place in the speed and strength training of taekwondists is occupied by the development of jumping ability, for which jumps with weights, "multi-jumps", jumps up and "in depth" with a rebound are used. It should be remembered that speed-strength training should be carried out with athletes who are able to mobilize to perform speed exercises at the limit or near-limit levels, and they should be carried out for a short time with rest intervals until almost complete recovery. Exercises should be performed before the first signs of fatigue (decrease in speed) appear. The flexibility of an athlete is determined mainly by the elasticity of the muscles and ligaments, which, in turn, depend on a number of factors: - ambient temperature (the higher the temperature, the higher the elasticity of the muscles); - daily periodicity (in the morning the flexibility is slightly lower than in the evening); - conditions of the central nervous system (in an excited state, muscle

elasticity increases, which manifests itself during competitions); -structures of joints. It is easier to develop flexibility in childhood, but athletes achieve the greatest mobility in joints by the age of 10-16, at an older age, joint mobility indicators decrease. There is a negative relationship between the 16 indicators of flexibility and strength. Excessive enthusiasm for the development of flexibility affects the strength and speed-strength capabilities of athletes, therefore, it should be reasonable to combine flexibility exercises with strength exercises and develop it to the necessary level that ensures the free execution of movements. Exercises aimed at developing flexibility are included in the warm-up of each training session and can form special training programs, however, given the specifics of taekwondo activities, it is more rational to combine the development of flexibility with strength and speed-strength training, which will allow maintaining the muscle tone and speed qualities necessary for taekwondists, while improving plasticity and mobility in the joints. Endurance is considered by the theory and methodology of physical culture as the ability to resist fatigue, which develops in the process of repeated repetition of exercises during training and competitions. In the process of repeated exercise, in addition to physical, sensory and emotional fatigue develops. The training of taekwondo endurance is considered as an increase, firstly, of general endurance, which provides for an increase in the functional capabilities of the muscles and heart; secondly, of special endurance, i.e. ability to perform exercises repeatedly without reducing the quality. General physical fitness exercises, mainly of a cyclical nature (running, walking, swimming, sports games), serve as a means of educating general endurance. The means of training special endurance are exercises with projectiles, exercises performed to failure, with a partner in pairs, conditional and free-style duels. When cultivating endurance, it is necessary to ensure that classes do not lead to persistent nervous fatigue, which is expressed in deterioration and loss of sleep, emotional downturns, etc. To do this, at the first signs of excessive fatigue and sleep disorders, it is necessary to reduce the special load and apply restorative means. In the process of physical training of children, it is necessary to remember about the sensitive periods of development of individual physical qualities. The most intensive development of speed and strength qualities in boys is up to 17 years old. The relative strength of boys develops most intensively until the age of 13-14, then the growth rate decreases slightly, and after, upon reaching biological maturity, with directed training, a noticeable increase is again observed. Flexibility develops most easily in childhood, when the muscles and ligaments are most elastic, with an increase in muscle mass, the mobility indicators in the joints deteriorate. Coordination of movements is well developed in children of primary school age, which allows them to master complex

movements. During puberty, there is often a deterioration in coordination of movements and a decrease in sports results, which is temporary and is associated with the peculiarities of the biological maturation of the athletes' body.

Conclusion: Each sport has its own level of strength development, depending on the specifics of the sport and the conditions of manifestations of strength. Thus, the maximum strength of the extensors and flexors of the forearm in taekwondo athletes is at a fairly high level, while the maximum strength of the back muscles lags behind in terms of indicators from other sports. The holistic method is the main one in the education of the taekwondo specialist's special strength. It is characterized by the simultaneous improvement of both the fighter's power capabilities and his special skills.

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